

IoT Based Crop Monitoring Drone Using Mobile App

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Abstract

Drone technology is changing farming by enabling real-time data collection and analysis to support better decisions. This research focuses on creating an IoT-based crop monitoring system using drones and a mobile app. The goal is to use resources more efficiently, keep crops healthy, and increase production. The drone is equipped with humidity sensors and cameras to capture high-resolution images of the crops. These images help identify problems like pests, diseases, and nutrient shortages. Improving this system can help solve problems that lead to low crop yields and improve how farmers track and manage their fields.

Keywords—drones ,crop ,monitoring ,food.

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is an essential industry worldwide, especially as the global population continues to grow. Traditional farming methods often rely on manual checks and general practices, which can lead to poor use of resources and lower crop productivity. In recent years, the use of technology in farming known as smart agriculture or precision farming has become a practical way to solve these problems. Smart agriculture uses technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), drones, remote sensing, and artificial intelligence (AI) to make farming more efficient and sustainable. IoT devices like sensors can measure real-time data on soil quality, weather, and crop conditions. Drones equipped with cameras and sensors can scan large fields and track crop growth with high accuracy.

In India, agriculture plays a key role in the economy. Improving farming output and ensuring safe conditions for farmers is vital. A 2018 survey showed that 9.2% of the world's population faced serious food shortages. Another 17.2% struggled with moderate food insecurity, meaning they didn't have steady access to enough food. In total, around 26.4% of people were affected by both moderate and severe food access problems. The COVID-19 pandemic made things worse by disrupting food supply chains and delaying critical farming inputs like labor, seeds, fertilizers, and pesticides, which led to reduced crop yields.

This research paper presents an IoT-based crop monitoring system that uses drones and a mobile app. The system is designed to be easy to use and helps monitor crop health,

manage resources efficiently, and increase crop yield. By collecting and analyzing real-time data, farmers can make better decisions, leading to more productive and sustainable farming.

Purpose Of Design Agriculture Crop Monitoring Drone

Creating an IoT-based crop monitoring drone is key to improving modern farming by increasing efficiency, sustainability, and productivity. The system collects and analyzes real-time data, helping to detect crop diseases early and manage resources more effectively. Drones equipped with sensors and cameras measure important environmental and plant health factors like temperature and humidity. This data gives farmers a clear and accurate view of their crops and field conditions. Detecting pests and diseases early helps prevent large-scale damage and reduces crop losses. The collected data is processed to give farmers useful insights, leading to better decisions and improved farming results

Fig.Block Diagram

With the global population increasing rapidly, ensuring enough food for everyone is becoming a major challenge. By 2050, global food production must grow by about 50% to feed an estimated 10 billion people. In India, nearly two-thirds of the population depends on agriculture for their livelihood. However, many Indian farmers still use traditional methods for crop monitoring and fertilizer application, which are often slow and inefficient. Events like the COVID-19 pandemic made it even harder for farmers using these methods.

To address these challenges, this project aims to develop a stable drone system that can capture images of farmland. These images help detect damaged or decaying crops and track different stages of crop growth and health. Drone technology offers an efficient solution for agricultural monitoring. By analyzing drone-collected data, farmers and agricultural experts—especially in rural areas—can improve their practices and increase crop yields.

Fig:CropMonitoringdrone

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Drones designed for agriculture have the potential to improve crop yields and transform farming practices. Farmers can use these drones to monitor their fields more effectively. Across the world, various types of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) are used in agriculture—most are small drones equipped with special cameras for observing crop conditions. In this project, drones are used to capture images of plants in the field. These images help identify issues like crop damage or decay early, allowing farmers to take quick action and improve overall harvest quality

Fig.live data of temperature and humidity

The following image represents a *Bean Plant*, which is analyzed using the Plantix mobile application for comparison and diagnosis purposes.

Result No 1

Before Analysis

Fig:Bean Plant

1 Diagnosis result Change

Healthy Plant

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2 Recommendations

Tips to keep your plant healthy

- Fertilize with the right fertilizer mixture and a balanced nutrient supply
- Do not over-water the crop during the season
- Do not touch healthy plants after touching infected plants
- Maintain a high number of different varieties of plants around fields
- If treating against an infestation, use specific products that do not affect beneficial insects
- Remove diseased leaves, fruit or branches at the right time during the growing season
- After the harvest, clean up plant debris from the field or orchard and burn them
- In case of pests and diseases, always consider an integrated approach with preventive measures together with biological treatments if available

Diagnosis result

 Symptoms

- Tiny spots on leaves.
- Small webs between stem and leaf.
- Dried out leaves.
- Tiny, pale green, oval mites.

The spider mites feeding causes white to yellow speckles to form on the upper surface of the leaves. As infestation becomes more severe, leaves appear bronzed or silvery first and then become brittle, rip open between the leaf veins, and finally fall off. Spider mite eggs can be found on undersides of leaves. The spider mite itself is located there, nesting in a cocoon resembling webbing. Infected plants will be covered by a web spun by the spider mites. Shoot tips can become bald and as a result, side shoots start to grow. In cases of heavy damage, the quantity, as well as quality of fruits, is reduced.

Result No2

Before Analysis

Fig:Brinjal Plant

1 Diagnosis result Change

Spider Mites

Mite

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2 Recommended products

Recommended by Plantix

Based on active ingredient and availability

See product information on

OMITE
by Dhanuka Agritech L...

 40

Oberon
by Bayer

 207

Mo
by E

Additionally, the required amount of fertilizer can be calculated based on the field area and the specific crop type.

← **Fertilizer Calculator**

See relevant information on Black & Green... ▾

1 Nutrient quantities ⓘ

Based on your field size and crop, we've selected a nutrient ratio for you

[Edit](#)

N: 8 kg 8 kg/ac	P: 18 kg 18 kg/ac	K: 10 kg 10 kg/ac
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Unit

Acre Hectare Gunta

Plot size

Sizes smaller than one unit are expressed as 0.
Example: half acre = 0.5

— +

Acre

[Calculate](#)

FUTURE SCOPE

The payload capacity of quadcopters can be enhanced by either increasing the number of motors or using larger propellers, both of which contribute to greater thrust generation. Flight duration is primarily dependent on the drone's battery capacity, which determines how long the UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) can remain airborne. However, flight time can vary due to factors such as payload weight, weather conditions, and power consumption by onboard systems.

Integrating multiple sensors such as multispectral, thermal, and humidity sensors can significantly improve the accuracy and depth of data collected, enabling more precise monitoring of crop health. Digital Image Processing (DIP) techniques can be applied to aerial images captured by drones to identify dead or diseased plants and distinguish them from healthy ones. These methods use pattern recognition, color analysis, and vegetation indices (such as NDVI) to classify plant health, allowing for targeted intervention and improved field management.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the growing importance of UAVs in modern agriculture, particularly their role in precision farming through autonomous monitoring and real-time

data collection. By integrating UAVs into feedback-controlled systems, significant improvements in efficiency, resource usage, and crop management can be achieved. The future of agricultural UAVs promises major reductions in water, chemical, and labor costs. However, to fully realize their potential, advancements in flight performance and strict compliance with aviation regulations are essential for safe and effective deployment.

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